

LINGUISTIC AND LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL FEATURES OF TEXTS
AND HEADINGS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.

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Annotation.

The article presents linguistic, linguoculturological features of texts and headings in English and Uzbek, and also explores the similarities and differences between language and culture, Uzbek and English texts.

Аннотация.

В статье представлены лингвистические, лингвокультурологические особенности текстов и заголовков на английском и узбекском языках, а также исследованы сходства и различия между языком и культурой, узбекскими и английскими текстами.

This article provides information on the relevance of the problem of speech production today and the use of pedagogical technologies in speech production, scientific ideas, rules, types of methods.

Ключевые слова: *Лингвистические, лингвокультурологические, особенности, текст, заглавие, английский, узбекский, язык, изученный.*

Key words: *Linguistic, linguoculturological, feature, text, title, english, uzbek, language, researched.*

Introduction. The Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the independent states, recognized by all developed countries and having a place in the world community. News in all spheres of the life of the society of our country leads to the further prosperity of Uzbekistan.

Much attention paid to the educational process in our country makes a positive contribution to the education of young people. At the same time, due to the growing interest and demand for foreign languages in Uzbekistan, especially for English, new decisions and decrees on the teaching of foreign languages in the education system are being implemented throughout the country. The problem of speech formation is relevant today. The formation of speech in preschoolers is an important and complex task. The successful solution of this problem is necessary both for preparing children for the upcoming schooling and for comfortable communication with others. Therefore, the purposeful and varied work of the educator with children with the help of various innovative and developing technologies, the use of various forms of work with parents and teachers will lead to a positive dynamics in the development of the speech of preschoolers.

Material and Methods. This article describes the relationship between language and culture in the "Analysis of linguistic and cultural aspects of Uzbek and English headings", explores the thematic similarities of Uzbek and English proverbs, their mentality and national identity, we try to delve into such issues as character expression.

This article is devoted to the study of linguoculturological features of English phraseological units taken from various sources - language elements expressed in headings. preservation and transmission of national cultural experience, knowledge, stereotypes and values from generation to generation.

Linguistic and cultural analysis in phraseology allows us to fully reveal the specifics of phraseological units and describe their role in the linguistic conceptualization of the world. This article discusses phraseological units that not only describe what is happening in a figurative sense, but also simultaneously broadcast symbols, stereotypes, standards, mythologies that take on the function of a cultural symbol.[1]

There are many headline studies today. At the same time the study of all aspects of heading in the field of paremiology is one of the main functions. When examining the comparative aspects of headings we study their linguacultural aspects.

Language is the culture, values and beliefs of any nation as a whole is the most important factor in expressing the uniqueness of a nation. Linguist one of the scientists - Nida to study the language of the people and their culture says it's important. He emphasizes that language and culture are interrelated a similar system that has evolved. He explains it this way:

“Cultural factors are deeply intertwined with language and thus morphologically and structurally reflected in the forms of the language”.

Renowned linguist Sapir highlights the richness of the language formed through the physical and social atmosphere of humanity. And it's all theoretically, we can call language a part of culture.

On the example of cultural factors in general, the linguist Telia is known to the people and knowledge of one's history, traditions and values, daily habits, etc. Cultural indicators are the fundamental foundations of humanity and through them the world explains also, in his opinion, every culture the core language can never be learned in isolation from culture and humanity uses language to express all aspects of culture. As a linguist and folklorist, Telia emphasizes the role of paremiology in linking culture with language. He says that since language represents the entire culture, it is definitely a paremiology. The field can also express the culture of the people who speak this language in a very beautiful and deep way. Telia calls it:

“ if language contributes to the formation of a collective cultural identity, also paremiology, due its wide spectrum of different forms of usage and due to the fact that it often includes elements which have a strong relationship with the culture of a specific country (part of the body, animals, and colors), can be considered as a domain of linguistics which seems to adequately illustrate the correlation between culture and language. This suggests a new direction of research for proverb studies, called “linguo-cultural investigation”, or the analysis of proverbs for cultural data as represented in linguistic meanings”.[2]

Thus, titles today are one of the most active tools for the representation of folk culture in the process of linguoculturological research in linguistics. Becomes one of the important topics. The main object of many studies processed as. English and

Uzbek consideration of linguistic and cultural features of names and their similarities and learning about differences is one of the most important steps in our work. It's all thanks to a number of theories based on the theories of the above scientists in-depth analysis of our ideas in Uzbek and English we will try to prove.

Conclusion. So, while the knowledge and innovations studied by many scientists theoretically substantiated the proof of our ideas, some of the English and Uzbek words studied above reflect the characteristics of the English and Uzbek peoples from a linguistic and cultural point of view. It is significant that the same headings, proverbs, available in both languages, reveal their features, sometimes by the same people, sometimes with completely different expressions.

This is because what a nation has is also expressed in its language. If something or situation exists in both languages, the words often have the same meaning. If this is not the case, then the words may have completely different meanings, or alternatives to the same title may not exist at all in the compared language. In this regard, English and Uzbek headlines and proverbs reflect the traditions of the people from the past to the present, and proverbs, as a rare example of folklore, lead to this task.

When studying the mentality of Uzbeks and English, headlines and proverbs written in Uzbek and English can show similarities and differences between the two peoples.

LITERATURE

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